

ABOUT THE AMOUNT OF RESOURCES NECESSARY TO PERFORM THE CMIP6 SIMULATIONS

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Introduction

As part of the CPMIP (Computational Performance MIP), information about computational resources used for CMIP6 simulations was collected from European modelling groups in the framework of the IS-ENES3 project: climate model specifications, computers used, amount of core hours, type and size of the output, and other items. The bulk of this information was published by IS-ENES3 as deliverable D3.4¹, and with detailed analysis in Acosta et al (2024).

The purpose of this short note is to present a synthesis evaluation of the resources which were necessary to run the simulations by the various European groups, in terms of computing effort and data produced. This synthesis is extracted and extended from the detailed information in Acosta et al (2024). The present note was prepared and discussed by the ENES Models, Tools and HPC Task Force (MTHPC-TF), established jointly by the EU IS-ENES project and ESIWACE Centre of Excellence. It was also presented at the 7th ENES HPC Workshop in Barcelona (May 9-11, 2022), where it was further discussed. The results are put in context with what we know about CMIP5 resources used and data production, as well as expectations for CMIP7.

Parameters to be considered

The initial parameters of interest relate to:

- the output of the calculations: number of Simulated Years (SY) and amount of data (in petabytes, PB) sent for storage within the ESGF archive. These data are available for redistribution to all interested groups world-wide for further analysis, including, of course, the analysis prepared for the IPCC AR6;
- the amount of computational resources that were necessary to perform these simulations, in number of core-hours (CH).

These numbers are labelled as "ESGF".

The ESGF output and computational resources do not cover all the years simulated, and hence the total SY produced and total consumption of computational resources by the different groups in the course of their CMIP efforts. For example, preparatory simulations were performed for development and tuning purposes, and not all ensemble member data were submitted to the ESGF. A full accounting of the resources necessary for CMIP exercises needs to include these SY and their cost. While the number of SY in the ESGF archive and associated cost is relatively easy to calculate, the total number of SY and additional computational cost are only available as estimates. Where possible, the total effort in terms of ESGF and additional SY, core-hours or data was estimated by the modelling groups themselves; when it was not possible, the total effort was established here,

¹ Available on IS-ENES3 zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.6394048>

somewhat arbitrarily, using some proportionality rules (see below, “Method for estimating missing numbers”).

Method for estimating missing numbers

As the data necessary to estimate the resources used for the “total” simulations were not planned to be collected at the time the CMIP6 simulations started, some groups were not able to provide such numbers, while some others could, depending on their national allocation system and specific requests sent to their computing centres. When the “total” numbers were missing they have been estimated as follows:

- computing the mean value of the ratio between numbers for “ESGF” and “total” runs for the teams that were able to provide all numbers;
- applying this mean ratio to estimate the missing numbers for the other teams.

In this case, the estimated numbers are shown in red in the following table.

The synthesis table and main remarks

Nine European groups, running 7 different families of models², produced simulations for CMIP6 as shown in the left column of the table.

CMIP6 participating groups/ Model	SY that produced data sent to ESGF	Total SY	SY ratio ESGF/ total [%]	Data sent to ESGF [PB]	Total data [PB]	Data ratio ESGF/ total [%]	CH for ESGF [Mh]	CH total [Mh]	CH ratio ESGF/ total [%]
EC-Earth	28105	38854	72.3%	0.80	1.405	56.9%	31.30	46.50	67.3%
CNRM-CERFACS	47000	110000	42.7%	0.80	2.480	32.3%	160.00	365.00	43.8%
IPSL	75000	165000	45.5%	1.80	7.600	23.7%	150.00	320.00	46.9%
CCMC	965	1926	50.1%	0.27	1.460	18.5%	1.99	4.34	45.9%
UKMO	59000	117764	50.1%	1.20	13.960	8.6%	683.00	1491.00	45.9%
NERC	640	1277	50.1%	0.46	2.490	18.5%	55.50	121.20	45.9%
NCC-NORES2	34443	68749	50.1%	0.32	1.100	29.1%	27.23	80.00	34.0%
MPI	24175	35000	69.1%	1.92	10.380	18.5%	18.50	35.61	52.0%
DKRZ	1276	1321	96.6%	0.29	1.570	18.5%	5.52	5.90	93.6%
Sum	270604	539891	50.1%	7.86	42.445	18.5%	1133.04	2469.55	45.9%
CMIP5	98000			1.05	6.9+	15.2%	46.80		

These numbers should be taken with caution. They may look very different for the different groups in some cases. For example, the UKMO reports a much larger number of total data as compared to other centres. Some of these differences are due to the fact that some data from some ensemble

² Some groups include more than one laboratory; for example, the simulations using EC-Earth were jointly performed by a group of 3 laboratories (BSC, KNMI and SMHI). Also, different groups may share the same family of models, i.e., UKMO and NERC ran the Hadley model family, and MPI and DKRZ ran the MPI model family. Overall, we had 7 model families in both CMIP5 and CMIP6. Finally, we note that simulations performed by AWI do not appear neither for CMIP6 numbers, nor in the CMIP5 numbers.

members of some groups were not published on ESGF, and to tuning and spin-up runs which have probably not been included by all groups in their total numbers.

We also note that, while the “total” numbers are the same in the above table and in table 9 of Acosta et.al. (2024), the “ESGF” numbers of the former are not always the same as the “useful” numbers of the latter³. This is partly because the numbers for the present note and for Acosta et al (2024) were collected at different dates; but more importantly because the term “useful” in Acosta et al (2024), defined as “with scientific value”, is less restrictive than the concept of “being published on ESGF”. For example, UKMO included in their “useful” data some high frequency diagnostics that were not required by CMIP6 and therefore not published on ESGF.

Some general remarks can nevertheless result:

1. The sum of “ESGF” SY, which amounts to 270,604, represents half of the “total” SY estimated here (539,891).
2. The amount of data made available on the ESGF archive is close to 8 PB, while 5 times more (42.5 PB) were produced, and likely stored at local facilities (possibly only temporarily, given the total amount of such data);
3. The cost of the ESGF-published simulations (in terms of compute resource) is 1.133 billion core-hours, just below half of the total amount used (2.470 billion). This represents using one hypothetical million-core supercomputer for approximately 2,500 hours, *i.e.*, solidly over 3 months. It should be noted that the simulations were carried out entirely on national resources, as the PRACE contribution was minimal (see below).

Comparison with CMIP5, and very preliminary look forward CMIP7

The MTHPC-TF had previously attempted to calculate the effort needed to produce CMIP5 (see 10.5281/zenodo.10893931), and those numbers are shown in the table for comparison. One should keep in mind that uncertainties affect the interpretation of these CMIP5 numbers: they likely correspond to a mix between the “ESGF” and “total” reported for CMIP6, the mix being probably different from one team to the other. While in principle we could extract actual ESGF CMIP5 SY from the ESGF archive, we have not done so because these numbers, like those presented here for CMIP6, are simply snapshots in time. The numbers on the archive now probably differ for both CMIP5 and CMIP6.

Nevertheless, it is possible to draw a few lessons from the comparison between CMIP5 and CMIP6:

1. The number of ESGF SY has increased at least by a factor close to 3. Given the fact that the time horizon of simulations selected for the IPCC report has not changed very much, this roughly threefold increase likely arises from the larger number of experiments in CMIP6 and the larger ensembles produced.
2. The amount of computing resources (core-hours) has increased by a factor between ~25 (1133/46.8 for “ESGF” core-hours) and 50 (2470/46.8 for “total” core-hours). If we take into account that the number of SY has increased by a factor of 3, this means that a typical SY required between 8 and 16 times more resources for CMIP6 than for CMIP5. This large

³ In terms of Simulated Years (SY), numbers of “useful” SY from Acosta et al (2024) and “ESGF” SY from the above table are different for NCC-NorESM2 and UKMO; in terms of data, numbers of “useful” data from the Acosta et al (2024) and “ESGF” data from the above table are different for CMCC, CNRM-CERFACS, DKRZ and UKMO.

increase is certainly due to the increased resolution of the models used, and possibly as well to their increased complexity;

3. The amount of data which has been transferred to ESGF has increased by a factor of almost 8 (7.86/1.05), a number almost 3 times larger than the increase in SY. This likely reflects the increased resolution of CMIP6 simulations and the larger data request in CMIP6 ;
4. If one simply, and probably a bit unrealistically⁴, extrapolates the tendency in required computing resources from CMIP5 to CMIP6, i.e an increase between 25 and 50, to CMIP7, one would anticipate an additional 1 to 2 orders of magnitude of required compute for CMIP7. Such an increase is only possible given sufficient extra computing resources, which, at least at the time of writing, would likely need to be predominantly CPU based. This may be problematic given that the largest computers now mainly utilise accelerators. However, even if the computing resources are available, the number of SY might remain in the same range, with an only modest increase in demand for the IPCC simulations (and no foreseen participation from new European teams); but given the expected increase in spatial resolution and complexity of models, the further increase of data production in CMIP7 could be up to 1 order of magnitude.

Other remarks

It could be of interest to realise that, during the time when a large fraction of national computing resources was used for the CMIP6 simulations, the resources provided by PRACE were used only marginally for these simulations, *i.e.*, for a maximum of 80 million core-hours as compared to the total of 2470 million, that is only 3% of the overall effort. During the same period, PRACE allocated approximately 1,000 millions of core-hours to other projects and groups active in climate, oceanography and geophysical flows. While these groups were able to submit proposals to the PRACE competitive calls, this was generally not possible for CMIP6 simulations for which allocations have to be known much in advance to fulfil international commitments. This dichotomy between research supported by PRACE and production supported by national facilities might not be sustainable for running CMIP7, an issue which would have to be discussed soon within EuroHPC. Issues at stake would concern both multi-year allocations, known early enough before the CMIP7 production would start, and access to computers adapted to the climate simulations.

Energy and carbon footprint aspects

A question which has to be further considered is the carbon footprint of CMIP6, including computing, data exchange and data storage for further analysis. Some of these issues are addressed in Acosta et al (2024), which looks at not only the total energy required for CMIP6 simulations, but also the way electricity is produced in different countries where the computations are being made (fossil fuels, nuclear, renewables). There it is estimated that ~50 TeraJoules (*i.e.*, ~ 14 000 MWh) were necessary for running the different simulations and producing the data, leading to 1692 tons of CO₂.

The additional cost of moving the data is not discussed here, as it is a very difficult task to evaluate. Nonetheless, based on Aslan et al. 2017, our best estimate for data transfer is 30 Wh/GB (*i.e.* 60 Wh/GB in 2015 taking into account a decrease by half in 2017 when the CMIP6 runs were performed), leading to 236 MWh for ~8 PB of data (*i.e.* much less for data transfer than for data production). This estimate is fraught with uncertainty and does not include unknown energy

⁴ Given the definition of CMIP7 has not been finalised yet, this is a difficult extrapolation but there is evidence that the desire for new experiments, bigger ensembles, and models with higher resolution and more complexity is continuing as it ever did.

demand for end-user download and actual data analysis. Furthermore, we cannot assign the cost to any particular country (and hence associate a particular form of energy production).

There are additional energy costs associated with the data storage itself, which we have not yet been able to quantify, but we believe these would likely be an order of magnitude less than for the production of the data.

Future CMIP7 simulations will obviously be constrained by energy costs and CO₂ emissions. This will call for being more cautious about running only necessary simulations and avoiding to produce, store and exchange data that would never be analysed. A set of best practices seems to be highly desirable, to be shared between contributing groups.

References

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